

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

EM-TECH - Innovative e-motor technologies covering e-axles and e-corners vehicle architectures for high-efficient and sustainable e-mobility

HORIZON-CL5-2022-D5-01-09

GA No. 101096083

Work package No.	1
Deliverable No.	D1.2
Expected delivery date	30.06.2023
Actual submission date	30.06.2023
Lead beneficiary	AIG
Dissemination level	PU

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

History

Date	Version Number	Comment
11.05.2023	0.1	Initial Draft
17.05.2023	0.2	First review and consolidation by AIG
25.05.2023	0.3	Feedback from lawyer and GDPR expert on the overall approach and integration of the comments by AIG; integration of PO7 and PO8 by USR.
01.06.2023	0.4	Integration of project management and CDE related datasets by AIG
05.06.2023	0.5	Enhancement of the data flow charts (Section 6)
06.06.2023	0.6	Consolidation based on the workshop with external lawyer and GDPR expert, especially on purpose and target of the document, and on regulations to follow
21.06.2023	0.7	Integration of the dataset detailed description of the PO6 by UG.
22.06.2023	0.8	Integration of the dataset description of the PO4 by POLITO, PO6 & PO10 by TUI, and PO5 by I&M
26.06.2023	0.9	Integration of the dataset description of the PO2 by VAI and PO3 by UBATH
26.06.2023	0.10	Integration of the dataset description of the PO1 by ELA and PO9 by AVL
28.06.2023	0.11	Compilation of complete draft for final review
29.06.2023	0.12	Final review
30.06.2023	1.0	Final version for submission.

Authors

Name, Partner	E-mail
Eric Armengaud, AIG	eric@armengaud.at
Anna Zamecnik	anna.zamecnik@armengaud.at
Martin Weinzerl, AVL	martin.weinzerl@avl.com
Jasmin Kniewallner, AVL	Jasmin.Kniewallner@avl.com
Viktar Beliautsou, TUIL	viktar.beliautsou@tu-ilmenau.de
Valentin Ivanov, TUIL	valentin.ivanov@tu-ilmenau.de
Nicola Amati, POLITO	nicola.amati@polito.it

Ezio Spessa, POLITO	ezio.spessa@polito.it
Gorazd Lampic, ELA	Gorazd@elaphe-ev.com
Matic Herzog, ELA	matic.herzog@elaphe-ev.com
Yannick Dominik, VAIONIC	ydominik@vaionic.de
Lennart Leopold, VAIONIC	lleopold@vaionic.de
Claudio Romano, I&M	claudio.romano@ideasandmotion.com
Alejandro Robles Martin, UG	alejandro.robles-martin@urbangold.at
Aldo Sorniotto, USR	a.sorniotti@surrey.ac.uk
Bo Wang, USR	bo.wang@surrey.ac.uk
Umberto Montanaro, USR	u.montanaro@surrey.ac.uk
Chris Vagg, UBATH	crm20@bath.ac.uk

Reviewers

Name, Partner	E-mail
Umberto Montanaro, USR	u.montanaro@surrey.ac.uk
Nicola Amati, POLITO	nicola.amati@polito.it
Charles Waters, USR	charles.waters@surrey.ac.uk
Ingrid Armengaud, AIG	ingrid@armengaud.at

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Version
AFM	Axial Flux Motor
AVL	AVL List GmbH
CA	Consortium agreement
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CAN	Controller Area Network
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation
DEM	Demonstrator
DMP	Data management plan
ELA	Elaphe Propulsion Technologies
EoL	End-of-life

EU	European Union
FAIR data	Findable, accessible, interoperable, reuseable data
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
I&M	Ideas & Motion S.r.l.
IWM	In-Wheel Motor
LC(S)A	Life cycle (sustainability) analysis
LCA	Life cycle analysis
LCC	Life cycle costing
M	Month
N	No
PO	Project Outcome
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
R	Report
TUI	Technical University of Ilmenau
UBATH	University of Bath
UG	UrbanGold GmbH
USR	University of Surrey
VAI	Vaionic Technologies GmbH
XIL	X-in-the-Loop
Y	Yes

Table of Contents

- 1 Introduction 7
- 2 Methodology overview: Horizon Europe Template 9
 - 2.1 Horizon Europe Template on Data Management Plan 9
 - 2.2 Data flow 11
- 3 EM-TECH – overview of expected project outcomes and project operations 12
 - 3.1 EM-TECH expected project outcomes 12
 - 3.2 EM-TECH project operation 14
- 4 EM-TECH project steering and general approach on data management 16
 - 4.1 EM-TECH project structure and decision levels 16
 - 4.2 Comments on general points from the data management template 17
 - 4.3 EM-TECH general strategy on data management..... 18
- 5 Dataset detailed description..... 20
 - 5.1 Dataset related to PO1: High torque density radial flux in-wheel motor and drive series for electric vehicles with high voltage systems..... 20
 - Design of the IWM 20
 - Control strategy of the IWM..... 21
 - Simulation models of the IWM..... 22
 - Analysis, simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the IWM 23
 - 5.2 Dataset related to PO2: High power density axial flux on-board motor and drive series for electric vehicles with high voltage systems..... 23
 - Design of the AFM 23
 - Control strategy of the AFM 24
 - Simulation models of the AFM 26
 - Analysis, simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the AFM..... 27
 - Transmission design..... 28
 - 5.3 Dataset related to PO3: Electric gearing for in-wheel motors..... 29
 - Design of the electric gearing as part of the IWM design 29
 - Simulation results for electric gearing..... 30
 - 5.4 Dataset related to PO4: Virtual sensing technologies for enhancing motor operation 31
 - Simulation models of the virtual sensors 31

Digital twin (control strategy).....	32
Simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the virtual sensing technologies	34
5.5 Dataset related to PO5: Novel electric inverter/motor control functions based on virtual sensing technologies.....	35
Design of the inverter for AFM.....	35
Control strategy of the AFM inverter	36
Simulation models for the AFM inverter	37
Analysis, simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the AFM inverter	38
5.6 Dataset related to PO6: Use of recycled permanent magnets in traction machines	39
Recyclability / circularity designs.....	39
5.7 Dataset related to PO7: Novel electric drive control functions benefitting from the increased electric machine dynamics	40
Control strategy of the IWM and AFM	40
Simulation models of the IWM and AFM	41
Analysis, simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the IWM and AFM.....	42
5.8 Dataset related to PO8: Digital twinning of electric drives.....	44
Simulation models of the electric drive.....	44
Digital twin of the electric drive (control strategy)	45
Simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the Digital twinning of electric drives.....	46
Transmission virtual validation	47
5.9 Dataset related to PO9: Engineering services for electric drive LCA and LCC	48
LC(S)A reports for IWM and AFM	48
5.10 Dataset related to PO10: E Distributed XIL and innovative testing methodologies.....	50
XIL mechanical design.....	50
Real-time data during XIL distributed operation	51
XIL test results for IWM	52
XIL test results for AFM.....	53
5.11 Dataset related to project operation and CDE activities:	55
Contact list with personal contact information.....	55
Project management related datasets	56

	Materials for Communication / Dissemination / Exploitation activities and reporting (e.g., deliverables, scientific papers, public presentations, marketing material, website content)	57
6	Data flow charts	59
7	Conclusion.....	61
7.1	Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions.....	61

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: TEMPLATE FOR DATA FLOW DESCRIPTION	11
FIGURE 2: EM-TECH AT-A-GLANCE	12
FIGURE 3: EM-TECH PROJECT STRUCTURE AND DECISION LEVELS	16
FIGURE 4: DATA FLOW CHART FOR CONTACT LIST MANAGEMENT	59
FIGURE 5: DATA FLOW CHART FOR RELEASE OF PROJECT DOCUMENTATION AND CDE MATERIALS.....	60
FIGURE 6: DATA FLOW CHART FOR CREATION AND VALIDATION OF TECHNICAL PROJECT OUTCOMES	60

List of Tables

TABLE 1: EM-TECH PROJECT OUTPUTS AND RELATED DATASETS	13
TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF PROJECT STRATEGY TOWARDS COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND EXPLOITATION.....	14
TABLE 3: EM-TECH PROJECT OPERATION AND RELATED DATASETS	15

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe project EM-TECH brings together 10 participants from industry and academia to develop novel solutions to push the boundaries of electric machine technology for automotive traction.

The target of this deliverable (related to Task T1.5) is to provide an initial data management plan (DMP) identifying the relevant datasets in EM-TECH and describing how these datasets will be managed. This DMP will be updated in Month M30 with the consolidated datasets identified and managed in the project.

The approach relies on the description of the expected project outcomes and activities planned during project operation to systematically identify relevant datasets. In a second step, the management of the identified datasets is described. This activity has several targets:

- At **project management level**, to ensure that all the project activities (and the respective datasets created in this context) have been carefully planned at operational level. Especially, to ensure that no major activities are missing, that each activity and dataset has an owner and defined processing rules.
- At **partner level**, to raise awareness on data management and provide guidance on relevant dataset categories in the project and how to manage the datasets accordingly.
- At **stakeholder level**, to provide information about the datasets managed in the project, and especially the datasets planned to be shared in the context of the open research strategy. The sharing of project documentation (e.g., deliverables, scientific publications) and sharing of datasets is an explicit strategy to strengthen the innovation ecosystem around the EM-TECH project.

In total, >30 datasets have been identified and classified into the following categories:

- (a) Datasets with **confidentiality issues**; Unintended disclosure of the dataset might lead to a loss of competitiveness for one or more partner(s) (e.g. datasets with elements protected by IPR (including the sui generis protection for databases) or trade secrets rules (cf. Directive (EU) 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure [1])).
- (b) Datasets with **cyber-security issues**; Modification of the dataset (unintended or malicious) might lead to issues related to loss of vehicle integrity or emergence of safety risk during operation (cf. the new NIS Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 [2] and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive)), or the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 [3]).
- (c) Datasets including **personal data**; Unintended access might lead to privacy issues, lack of management might lead to non-compliance regarding relevant national and European regulations (e.g., GDPR [4]).

- (d) Datasets to be published in the context of **open research data** and ones that could be impacted by access rights exercised by third parties based e.g. on the **PSI Directive** n° 2 (Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast) [5]) or the **Data Governance Act** (Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act)) [6] or the **Data Act** Proposal (Regulation on the fair access to and use of data (COM(2022) 68 final) (2022/0047(COD)) [7]).

The deliverable is organized as follows: Section 2 includes the data management plan template from Horizon Europe [8] to provide clarity on the official methodology. Section 3 provides project related information, especially the main expected project outcomes and discussion on related datasets. Section 4 focuses on information about the operation and steering of the project, and general approach for data management. This is refined in Section 5, which provides a detailed overview of the datasets and how these datasets will be managed; Section 6 describes the most relevant data flows, while Section 7 concludes this document.

2 Methodology overview: Horizon Europe Template

2.1 Horizon Europe Template on Data Management Plan

Disclaimer: this section has been extracted from the data management plan template from Horizon Europe [1] – Section 1 and 2. Target of this Section is to provide guidance for the contributors, and for the reader transparency on the methodology to be deployed later. Sections 3-7 of the data management plan template will be addressed in the next section.

This table will be used as template in Section 5 for the detailed description of the datasets.

1. Data Summary	
<p>Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</p> <p>What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?</p> <p>What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p> <p>What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?</p> <p>What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?</p> <p>To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?</p>	
2. FAIR data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</p> <p>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</p> <p>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</p> <p>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</p>
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</p> <p>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?</p> <p>Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?</p> <hr/> <p>Data</p> <p>Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.</p> <p>If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g., patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</p>

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

	<p>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?</p> <p>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?</p> <p>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</p> <p>Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?</p> <p>Metadata</p> <p>Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CCO, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?</p> <p>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</p> <p>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g., in open-source code)?</p>
<p>2.3. Making data interoperable</p>	<p>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?</p> <p>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?</p> <p>Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g., other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p>How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g., readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</p> <p>Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?</p> <p>Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</p> <p>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</p> <p>Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.</p> <p>Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.</p>
<p>3. Data security</p>	
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p> <p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?</p>	

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

2.2 Data flow

Parallel to the template for dataset description of the previous section, a template for simplified data flow description is proposed in Figure 1. The target is to provide an overview about the main steps within the data flow. Especially, four groups of information are foreseen:

- INPUT – to describe the stakeholder who trigger the dataset-related activities and its target;
- PROCESSING – to describe the stakeholders involved in the management and processing of the data, as well as technical solutions used for this;
- LEGACY DATA – to describe potential legacy datasets used during the processing and thus identify possible dependencies;
- USAGE – to describe the planned usage of the data and sharing policy.

Figure 1: Template for data flow description

3 EM-TECH – overview of expected project outcomes and project operations

3.1 EM-TECH expected project outcomes

The mission of EM-TECH is to **support the uptake of affordable, sustainable, and user-centric e-mobility, while strengthening the European innovation and value creation chain for e-motor technology.** For that purpose, EM-TECH will develop novel solutions to push the boundaries of electric machine technology for automotive traction, through: i) innovative direct and active cooling designs; ii) virtual sensing functionalities for the high-fidelity real-time estimation of the operating condition of the machine; iii) enhanced machine control, bringing reduced design and operating conservativeness enabled by ii); iv) electric gearing to provide enhanced operational flexibility and energy efficiency; v) digital twin based optimisation, embedding systematic consideration of Life Cycle Analysis and Life Cycle Costing aspects since the early design stages; and vi) adoption of recycled permanent magnets and circularity solutions.

The proposed innovations will be implemented in new series of radial flux direct drive in-wheel motors characterised by so far unexplored levels of torque density (>150 Nm/litre, >50 Nm/kg), and on-board single stator double rotor type ironless axial flux machines providing power density and specific power levels in excess of 30 kW/litre and 10 kW/kg. The solutions will address both passenger car and van applications (continuous power levels of 50 kW - 120 kW), providing competitive costs (<6 Euro/kg for a production of 100000 units/year), and leading to significant reduction of motor energy loss during real vehicle operation (>25%), and to >60% decrease of the rare earth content, including implementation of magnet recycling solutions.

The project has been designed around five objectives (see Figure 2) to map the 10 project outcomes (PO) and the capabilities of the partners to the target groups, to ultimately create impact at scientific, technological, economic and societal point of views.

Figure 2: EM-TECH at-a-glance

The project outputs (equivalent to Key Exploitable Results) are the cornerstone for this DMP. Hence, the identification of the relevant datasets is relying on the systematic analysis of the key project activities (around the project outputs) and on the project management activities as described in the next paragraph.

Table 1: EM-TECH project outputs and related datasets

Project output (PO)	Involved Beneficiaries	Expected datasets
PO1. High torque density radial flux in-wheel motor and drive series for electric vehicles with high voltage systems	ELA, POLITO	Design of the IWM Control strategy of the IWM Simulation models of the IWM Analysis, simulation, and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the IWM
PO2. High power density axial flux on-board motor and drive series for electric vehicles with high voltage systems	VAI, I&M, AVL	Design of the AFM Control strategy of the AFM Simulation models of the AFM Analysis, simulation, and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the AFM Transmission design
PO3. Electric gearing for in-wheel motors	UBATH	Design of the electric gearing as part of the IWM design Simulation results for electric gearing
PO4. Virtual sensing technologies for enhancing motor operation	POLITO	Simulation models of the virtual sensors Digital twin (control strategy) Simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the virtual sensing technologies
PO5. Novel electric inverter/motor control functions based on virtual sensing technologies	POLITO, I&M	Design of the inverter for AFM Control strategy of the AFM inverter Simulation models for the AFM inverter Analysis, simulation, and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the AFM inverter
PO6. Use of recycled permanent magnets in traction machines	UG	Recyclability / circularity designs
PO7. Novel electric drive control functions benefitting from the increased electric machine dynamics	USR, TUI	Control strategy of the IWM and AFM Simulation models of the IWM and AFM

		Analysis, simulation, and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the IWM and AFM
PO8. Digital twinning of electric drives	AVL, TUI, USR	Simulation models of the electric drive Digital twin of the electric drive (control strategy) Simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the Digital twinning of electric drives Transmission virtual validation
PO9. Engineering services for electric drive LCA and LCC	AVL, POLITO	LC(S)A reports for IWM and AFM
PO10. Distributed XIL and innovative testing methodologies	TUI, USR, POLITO, UBATH, AVL	XIL mechanical design Real-time data during XIL distributed operation XIL test results for IWM XIL test results for AFM

3.2 EM-TECH project operation

Besides scientific and technology related activities, two further important groups of activities shall be additionally mentioned: project management including reporting, and Communication / Dissemination / Exploitation (CDE), see Table 2. Important aspects are related to the management of the relevant stakeholder communities, as well as preparation and release of dedicated materials (e.g., project summaries (text, graphics, video), reports, presentations, publications). Table 3 provides an overview of the related datasets.

Table 2: Overview of project strategy towards communication, dissemination, and exploitation

EM-TECH STRATEGY						
COMMUNICATION & OUTREACH						
Targets	Who	EU Citizens	EU Policy Makers	Public / Social Services	Young women	Scholars
	Why	Awareness of EU-funding as innovation enabler	Influencing decisions towards investments on 2ZERO topics	Promotion of clean and circular mobility technologies	Encouraging to engineering and research career	Triggering interest on science and technology
Channels		Web Channels	Public Media	Events and Actions on Consortium Level	Events and Actions on Community Level	
DISSEMINATION						
Targets	Industrial Actors Relevant to EM-TECH Project Outputs	EU Platforms and Initiatives	Professional societies (IEEE, SAE, FISITA)	Academics and Research Community		
Channels	Web Channels	Research / Innovation Presentations	Open Access Publications	Professional Societies Platforms	Advocate Ecosystem Platforms	
EXPLOITATION						

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

Targets	OEMs and Suppliers of Automotive Systems	Electric Powertrain Developers	Automotive Testing Equipment Developers	Operators of electrified transport services
Channels	IP Protection and Patenting of EM-TECH Project Outputs	Industrial and Research Showcasing of EM-TECH Project Outputs		Partners' marketing and sales channels

Table 3: EM-TECH project operation and related datasets

Project activity	Involved Beneficiaries	Expected datasets
Meeting organization	Coordinator / Meeting organizer	Contact list with personal contact information
Daily management	Project management team	Project management related datasets
Communication / Dissemination management and reporting	Partner having created the material	Materials for Communication / Dissemination / Exploitation activities and reporting

4 EM-TECH project steering and general approach on data management

4.1 EM-TECH project structure and decision levels

The project coordination is based on a philosophy of **management by objectives**, in which delegation of responsibility, communication, trust and realistic objectives are the key to the management structure. Management activities have been distributed considering the different levels in the structure, **empowering the WP leaders and principal investigators to assume a leading role in the technical management**. The management team (consortium lead: AVL, daily management by all WP leaders) is composed by managers presenting long-term experience for the management of collaborative programs of this size.

Figure 3 summarizes the decision structure of EM-TECH.

Figure 3: EM-TECH project structure and decision levels

Project management (implemented in T1.1): Project management is set up to ensure compliance of all project activities with the objectives set out in the Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement, and the relevant annexes. To achieve this aim, the project management structure will maintain a continuous flow of communication and information to and between all partners as well as the European Commission. The project management is divided into 2 levels: 1) technical coordination and 2) administrative project management. The technical coordinator focuses on the technical execution of the work ensuring effective project planning, risk management and information flow within the consortium and alignment between work packages. The technical coordinator is supported by an administrative project leader on the aspects of financial, legal, and administrative project management. The project management is acting as single point of contact to the European Commission.

Work-package leader board (WPL, implemented in T1.3): It is the 1st level decision making body. It is within the WP Leader Board's responsibility to ensure and monitor proper cross-WP cooperation including timing of deliverables and risk monitoring; decide technical matters that affect more than one WP; assure quality of deliverables by reviewing deliverables and project results; report to the Project Steering Board on continuous basis; escalate to the Project Steering Board when considered as necessary. Each WP Leader will be responsible for the delivery of their respective work package and communication with

partners inside the WP to ensure and monitor execution of tasks according to time and resource plan. Deviations and risks will be identified inside the WP Leader Board and mitigation plans implemented.

Project steering board (PSB, implemented in T1.2): The Board’s responsibilities include (a) decisions on the strategic orientation of the project; (b) highest decision-making body for topics not finding a resolution in the WP Leader Board; (c) Quality Management (release of deliverables).

Innovation manager (implemented in T7.4): The target of this task is the management of the innovations created in the EM-TECH project. This consists of the update of the project output list, using cross-references, by continuously screening the project outputs and identifying the owner, IPR, communication channels and path for exploitation.

Scientific advisor: The scientific advisory board is composed of Prof. Aldo Sorniotti (WP2), Prof. Valentin Ivanov (WP5) and Prof. Nicola Amati (WP6) with the target to coordinate the scientific advances of the project and provide recommendation of the project management team.

Data management (implemented in T1.5): The target of this task is the setup and the maintenance of a data management plan (DMP – this deliverable), thereby supporting (a) the identification of datasets managed in the project, (b) the provision of guidance how to appropriately manage the datasets as support for the dataset owners.

4.2 Comments on general points from the data management template

Some aspects from the data management template from Horizon Europe [1] have not been addressed in the methodology discussed in Section 3, since they are related to project operations – and are addressed in this section.

Other research outputs

The approach for this deliverable is primarily focusing on the datasets to be generated throughout project execution. Through the “Project outcomes” (Section 3.1), this DMP is addressing the management of research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects, too. This is performed through the management of the datasets required for the design / validation / evaluation of the project outcomes.

Ethics

Within the course of EM-TECH, it is expected to encounter dataset sensitivities with respect to confidentiality, privacy, and cyber-security issues. While submitting this deliverable, no issue with respect to ethics could be identified so far, and no biometric data (as defined in GDPR) is planned to be used during the project. This situation will be continuously screened during the project execution.

Allocation of resources

The required resources for making data FAIR are foreseen (a) in WP1 / Task T1.5 for the coordination of the activity, as well as creation and management of the framework, (b) in WP2-WP7 to apply the framework according to the datasets identified.

Data security: a dedicated SharePoint managed by partner AVL is in place to enable efficient data sharing within the consortium members. This SharePoint is managed by AVL IT according to industrial standards, thereby addressing relevant regulations and to protect privacy and all personal data acquired for the project.

Other issues

At this stage, there is no plan to make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.

4.3 EM-TECH general strategy on data management

During the preparation of this deliverable, three criticality attributes for the datasets could be identified (*confidentiality, cyber-security, privacy*). A general approach is provided in this section to increase the readability of the document. The approach might be refined at dataset level in the next section in case a deviation to this general approach should be required. It is understood that a dataset might combine different criticalities; in this case, the different approaches described below should be applied.

Confidentiality: Unintended disclosure of the dataset might lead to a loss of competitiveness for one or more partner(s).

Some datasets could contain elements protected by IPR (including the sui generis protection for databases) or trade secrets rules (cf. Directive (EU) 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure) [1]).

This typically concerns information required for the design / validation / evaluation of project outcomes (e.g., CAD files from the e-motor). As far as possible, these data will be exchanged through the dedicated SharePoint with clear indication of the author's institution. All consortium members are aware of the confidentiality of these documents and will not disclose any information outside of the consortium without explicit release by the authors' institutions, and following the rules set in the Consortium Agreement. For some highly sensitive information (e.g., e-motor design), this information will not be distributed within the EM-TECH consortium; however, a dedicated contact point at e-motor partner is available to answer the specific requests required to efficiently advance in the project.

An additional aspect addresses project management and communication / dissemination activities. In this context, the released process for publications, deliverables, and other public information – as described in the consortium agreement – will be the general rule.

Cyber-security: Modification of the dataset (unintended or malicious) might lead to issues related to loss of vehicle integrity or emergence of safety risk during operation.

This typically addresses datasets for predictive control. Hence, external information – such as ones from the infrastructure or from other vehicles – might be considered for the control of the vehicle's critical function, finally raising issues related to vehicle integrity or functional safety.

The general approach will be to perform combined threat and risk analysis to understand possible impact of erroneous / missing data, and deploy appropriate counter measures (e.g., plausibility checks, redundancy, degradation mode), taking into account relevant requirements that could stem from the new **NIS Directive** (Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union [2], amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive)), or from the Proposal for a **Regulation** of the European Parliament and of the Council **on horizontal cybersecurity requirements** for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020, COM/2022/454 final) [3] (if adopted).

Personal data: Unintended access might lead to privacy issues; lack of management might lead to non-compliance regarding relevant national and European regulations

This concerns two groups of activities: (a) evaluation activities requiring the contribution of a human and identification of the task performed, such as testbench operation or vehicle demonstrator operation; in this case, operator information together with its activities might be logged together with the test results; and (b) project operation with the management of internal and external communication and the creation of relevant contact lists.

Regarding (a), the general rule will be to anonymize information, clearly identifying the operator from the vehicle related datasets or at least to comply with the minimization principle (using and processing as little as possible personal data) and the other requirements from the GDPR [4]. This will be performed e.g., by replacing name or other person related information by information related to execution date and content. Note that this is already state of practice at the EM-TECH partner institutions. Regarding (b) the approach will be to minimize the amount of contact lists to manage and ensure a management according GDPR by the dataset owners.

Open research data: Datasets that could be impacted by access rights exercised by third parties

Open research data are datasets that could be impacted by access rights exercised by third parties based e.g. on the PSI Directive n° 2 (Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast)) [5] or the Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act)) [6] or the Data Act Proposal (Regulation on the fair access to and use of data (COM(2022) 68 final) (2022/0047(COD)) [7].

If not mentioned differently, open research data will be published through the OPENAIRE repository (www.openaire.eu) respectively ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/communities/em-tech/?page=1&size=20>), after having been released within the consortium according to the rules stated in the Consortium Agreement.

5 Dataset detailed description

5.1 Dataset related to PO1: High torque density radial flux in-wheel motor and drive series for electric vehicles with high voltage systems

Title	Design of the IWM					Owner	ELA
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	Y	Privacy	Y	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The collection of data concerns technical documentation of E-motor and E-motor components, specific E-motor design files in various formats and CAD files of the E-corner solution.</p> <p>Apart from baseline data which will be re-used for comparison purposes of the new EM-TECH E-motor solution, all data will be new and generated specifically for the EM-TECH project.</p> <p>All the mentioned data, files and documentation will be generated with an intent to develop a new E-corner solution and E-motor for the EM-TECH project.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The metadata regarding the new E-motor solution will mostly be technical data and will not be possible to reference or to tag due to the nature of the documents and files. Engineering report which will summarize the development steps and design targets will be referenced and tagged instead.						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	Data for E-corner which concerns project partners and their deliverables will be shared directly with the mentioned project partners and not uploaded to coordinator’s Sharepoint, the repository for the whole consortium. If needed the data will be uploaded to Sharepoint but with strict access and security due to privacy concerns and nature of the generated data						
	Data						
	The data regarding the E-corner will not be openly available.						
	Metadata						
	Metadata will be openly available in the form of an Engineering report and other PO related documentation.						
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Technical data vocabularies will be previously defined, referenced or exemplified in order to avoid misinterpretations among the involved partners.</p> <p>Qualified references will be pursued.</p>						
2.4. Increase data re-use	General data will not be freely available in the public domain. The data which is not directly related to the EM-TECH PO and PO documentation, reporting will not be useable by third parties during or after the project.						
3. Data security							
Data is and will be stored on ELA secured servers along with EM-TECH PO related documentation that is and will be stored on coordinators SharePoint repository.							

Title	Control strategy of the IWM					Owner	ELA
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	Y	Privacy	Y	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The collection of data concerns the control strategies to improve vehicle dynamics, safety and energy efficiency, subject to new E-corner solution developed in the project. Data regarding the target vehicles and the characterisation of the different prototypes or designs of new machines solutions will be collected for control design, in the form of vectors of numbers in the output format such as .csv or .mat (MATLAB data). The controller models will be coded using Simulink software and saved in the format of .slx files.</p> <p>Presentations and internal documents describing the control strategies will be mostly produced in .pptx and .docx formats. When containers were necessary .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-20 MB per file</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information about the control functions (e.g., ABS) and the control methods (e.g., nonlinear predictive control). The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords will be included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator will manage the access and security of the data repository which will be limited to project partners involved in E-corner testing and validation steps.</p>						
	<p>Data</p> <p>The data for new control strategies is not openly available. The access to data for machine characteristics follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						
	<p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>The selected formats of the research data, e.g., mat and .csv, allow to easily re-combine data coming from different data sets and different origins. Core IP will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.</p>						
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>The data will not be freely available in the public domain. The data produced in the project will not be useable by third parties.</p>						
3. Data security							
<p>The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint</p>							

Title	Simulation models of the IWM						Owner	ELA
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	Y	Privacy	Y	Open Research Data	N	
1. Data Summary								
<p>The collection of data concerns the build-up of the surrogate model of E-corner and E-motor to replace the original models when considering the computation resources. The surrogate models will be implemented as Simulink .slx format. The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-20 MB per file.</p> <p>Other simulation models will relate to CFD simulation and analysis for the purpose of developing a novel direct cooling solution, FEM simulation and analysis for the purpose of design optimization and pre-validation of a novel mechanical E-gear solution. These data will be of a larger size, in several tens of GBs. To saving online storage space and also due to IP related limitations only simplified models will be uploaded and the rest of the results will be presented within the Engineering report and via other PO and Deliverables.</p>								
2. FAIR data								
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. The metadata will provide general information of IWMs (e.g., category, rating, size). The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable.							
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.							
	Data The access to data for machine characteristics follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.							
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.							
2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be limited and protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.							
2.4. Increase data re-use	The data will not be freely available in the public domain. The data produced in the project will not be useable by third parties.							
3. Data security								
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint.								

Title	Analysis, simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the IWM					Owner	ELA
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	Y	Privacy	Y	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
The collection of data concerns tests results for component and E-corner level. Outcome of the various tests will be in the form of Engineering report, Test report, Analysis report for a newly developed E-corner solution.							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. The metadata will provide general information of IWMs (e.g., category, rating, size). The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable.						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.						
	Data The access to data for machine characteristics follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be limited and protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.						
2.4. Increase data re-use	The data will not be freely available in the public domain. The data produced in the project will not be useable by third parties.						
3. Data security							
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint.							

5.2 Dataset related to PO2: High power density axial flux on-board motor and drive series for electric vehicles with high voltage systems

Title	Design of the AFM					Owner	VAI
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
Based on the design of the 6 th generation prototype, an improved design will be developed. Existing design will be optimized for performance, cost and producibility in series production. SolidWorks data formats will be used during development. The final design will also be saved as .step files, technical drawings of the components as .pdf and a bill of materials as .xlsx.							
Documentation and presentations for internal use will be stored as both .pptx and .pdf.							
The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-20 MB per file and up to 1-2 GB for files generated from CAD software. The							

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

total data size is expected to be in the order of multiple GB.	
2. FAIR data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information with for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.
	Data The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software used to generate the models. The final design will include drawings.
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own polices.	

Title	Control strategy of the AFM				Owner	VAI/I&M	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N

1. Data Summary	
<p>The control strategy will ensure save operation of the AFM over livetime while utilizing maximum performance. The control strategy of the AFM will be enforced by the Inverter. See also “Control strategy of the AFM inverter”</p> <p>Documentation and presentations for internal use will be stored as both .pptx and .pdf.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of MBs.</p>	
2. FAIR data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information with for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p>
	<p>Data</p> <p>The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>
	<p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the hard- and software the control strategy was developed on.</p>
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
<p>Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own polices.</p>	

Title	Simulation models of the AFM					Owner	VAI
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>Several detailed individual simulations will be carried out on a component or system level to compute surrogate models that will be used in the system simulation to archive the targeted high-performance design of the AFM. The simulations will include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. electromagnetic simulation of rotor and stator using Ansys Maxwell 3D 2. mechanical simulations of rotor, stator, and housing in Ansys mechanical 3. thermal/fluid simulations in Ansys CFD of cooling channels <p>The models, meshes and simulation results will be stored for further analysis and easier re-use.</p> <p>Documentation and presentations for internal use will be stored as both .pptx and .pdf.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of GBs per model and up to 100 GB for results. The total data size is expected to be in the order of TBs.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information with for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p>						
	<p>Data</p> <p>The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						
	<p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software the models were developed in.</p>						
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from</p>						

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

<p>publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
<p>3. Data security</p>
<p>Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own polices.</p>

Title	Analysis, simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the AFM					Owner	VAI
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The performance of the AFM will be validated in EM-Tech. Additionally, the individual and system simulations models are to be validated for later re-use for optimization. To do so, tests will be carried out on component, system and vehicle level. The measurement data will be saved as .csv or similar to then be analysed in MATLAB and compared to the simulation results. The scripts used for analysis will be saved as MATLAB .m files and include in line documentation. The resulting plots and diagrams will be stored as both .png as well as .fig files.</p> <p>Documentation and presentations will be stored as both .pptx and .pdf.</p> <p>The raw data is expected to be in the order of hundreds of MB per test. The total data size is expected to be in the order of tens of GB.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information with for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	<p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p>						
	Data						
	<p>The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						
	Metadata						
	<p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software and parameters used to generate the specified data. Results will be documented in form of graphs and figures.</p> <p>Standard data formats will be used to save measurement raw data and will contain a setup description as well as test and experiment conditions.</p> <p>Scripts for result analysis will use standard formats and include inline documentation. Results will be documented in form of graphs and figures.</p>						

<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
<p>3. Data security</p>	
<p>Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own polices.</p>	

Title	Transmission design					Owner	AVL
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
<p>1. Data Summary</p>							
<p>Based on the design and the EM-characteristic of the AFM, an optimized transmission model concept will be generated to maximize overall efficiency (including electrical motor and mechanical losses) with respect to a given duty cycle related to plausible and real load points. The final transmission concept will provide information about transmission setup (number of gear stages), gear macro geometry (transmission ratio, gear teeth numbers, helix angle, ...) and number of gears.</p> <p>Documentation and presentations will be stored as both .pptx and .pdf.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of MBs.</p>							
<p>2. FAIR data</p>							
<p>2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information with for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>						
<p>2.2. Making data accessible</p>	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p>						
	<p>Data</p> <p>The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						

	<p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software and parameters used to generate the specified data. Results will be documented in form of graphs and figures.</p> <p>Standard data formats will be used to save measurement raw data and will contain a setup description as well as test and experiment conditions.</p> <p>Scripts for result analysis will use standard formats and include inline documentation. Results will be documented in form of graphs, figures and/or tables.</p>
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
<p>3. Data security</p>	
<p>Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own polices.</p>	

5.3 Dataset related to PO3: Electric gearing for in-wheel motors

Title	Design of the electric gearing as part of the IWM design					Owner	UBATH	
Confidentiality	N	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N	
<p>1. Data Summary</p> <p>To complete the design objectives of the project, multiple forms of data will be generated. Primary data will be in the format of 3D CAD data natively created in Autodesk Inventor. Secondary data will be engineering/ manufacturing drawings produced from this 3D data and saved in PDF format. This data is expected to be in the region of 500 individual files with an estimated data size of <1Gb.</p> <p>This data is all generated as a result of designing specifically for this project and the project deliverables.</p> <p>This data will be useful to anyone looking to use the final design of the outcome of the project.</p>								
<p>2. FAIR data</p>								

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Data will be identified through use of an excel spreadsheet saved within the project Sharepoint. This leading document will control the project item numbering scheme and thus in turn correlate to the item numbering of individual CAD models and representative engineering drawings of any concept and final designs. This Excel sheet will control issue of drawings, descriptions and key metadata. This data will then be searchable.</p> <p>3D CAD Designs will be saved within a dedicated project folder within the IAAPS CAD vault. This Vault is saved on a Microsoft Azure Virtual cloud server and is accessible from the IAAPS network.</p>
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>3D design data will be deposited on the IAAPS CAD vault system. This is a highly trusted repository. 2D engineering drawing data will be saved onto the Project Sharepoint folder.</p> <p>The IAAPS Cad vault system is only accessible from the IAAPS network and with a valid user account. Permission can only be granted by a current IAAPS Mechanical Engineer that is a Vault admin. (There will always be a minimum of two IAAPS employees that can grant this access).</p> <p>The project SharePoint folder is accessible to anyone who the project folder has been shared with, and access can be granted by current project folder admins.</p> <p>Data</p> <p>As above</p> <p>Metadata</p> <p>Only descriptive metadata used, IAAPS Ltd is using internal naming convention</p>
2.3. Making data interoperable	All drawings created for the design of this project will be created using drawing standards such as BS8888 and will therefore be interoperable by anyone with relevant engineering experience.
2.4. Increase data re-use	Data will be re-used as per the needs of the project
3. Data security	
The IAAPS Cad vault system is only accessible from the IAAPS network and with a valid user account. Permission can only be granted by a current IAAPS Mechanical Engineer that is a Vault admin. (There will always be a minimum of two IAAPS employees that can grant this access).	

Title	Simulation results for electric gearing					Owner	UBATH
Confidentiality	N	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>To complete the design objectives of the project, multiple forms of data will be generated. Primary data will be in the format of 3D CAD data natively created in Autodesk Inventor. Secondary data will be engineering/ manufacturing drawings produced from this 3D data and saved in PDF format. This data is expected to be in the region of 500 individual files with an estimated data size of <1Gb.</p> <p>This data is all generated as a result of designing specifically for this project and the project deliverables.</p> <p>This data will be useful to anyone looking to use the final design of the outcome of the project.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including	Data will be identified through use of an excel spreadsheet saved within the project SharePoint. This leading document will control the project item numbering scheme and thus in turn correlate to the item numbering of individual CAD models and representative engineering drawings of any concept and final designs. This Excel sheet will control issue of drawings, descriptions and key metadata. This data						

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

provisions for metadata	<p>will then be searchable.</p> <p>3D CAD Designs will be saved within a dedicated project folder within the IAAPS CAD vault. This Vault is saved on a Microsoft Azure Virtual cloud server and is accessible from the IAAPS network.</p>
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>3D design data will be deposited on the IAAPS CAD vault system. This is a highly trusted repository. 2D engineering drawing data will be saved onto the Project SharePoint folder.</p> <p>The IAAPS Cad vault system is only accessible from the IAAPS network and with a valid user account. Permission can only be granted by a current IAAPS Mechanical Engineer that is a Vault admin. (There will always be a minimum of two IAAPS employees that can grant this access).</p> <p>The project SharePoint folder is accessible to anyone who the project folder has been shared with, and access can be granted by current project folder admins.</p>
	<p>Data</p> <p>As above</p>
	<p>Metadata</p> <p>Only descriptive metadata used, IAAPS Ltd is using internal naming convention</p>
2.3. Making data interoperable	All drawings created for the design of this project will be created using drawing standards such as BS8888 and will therefore be interoperable by anyone with relevant engineering experience.
2.4. Increase data re-use	Data will be re-used as per the needs of the project
3. Data security	
The IAAPS Cad vault system is only accessible from the IAAPS network and with a valid user account. Permission can only be granted by a current IAAPS Mechanical Engineer that is a Vault admin. (There will always be a minimum of two IAAPS employees that can grant this access).	

5.4 Dataset related to PO4: Virtual sensing technologies for enhancing motor operation

Title	Simulation models of the virtual sensors				Owner	POLITO	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The data regarding this section concerns the development of a permanent magnet virtual temperature sensing algorithm. Data regarding the target application (i.e., IWM) will be obtained from a simulation model of the direct drive, comprising of numeric vectors in an output format such as .csv and .mat (MATLAB data). Furthermore, data relating to machine parameters (i.e., materials) may be included in the development of the algorithm for improved estimation capability. This data is provisioned to stem from the parametrization of models related to the electric machines. The virtual sensing method will be implemented using Simulink software or Python script and saved in the format of .slx or .py files. Data made available by other partners for verification of the temperature sensing algorithm may be used, in addition to data obtained from previous FEM analyses.</p> <p>Presentations and internal documents describing the virtual sensors will be produced in .pptx and .docx formats. To compress a collection of files, .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>Given the model file format, the expected size is provisioned to be in the tens of kB. MATLAB data may have the order of GB due to large number of data points used for the development of the algorithm.</p>							

2. FAIR data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. The metadata will provide general information about the virtual sensors and their performance. The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation, used for reference of development and implementation of the algorithm. Search keywords will be included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.
	Data The data for developed virtual sensing algorithms and models is not openly available until related scientific papers are published. The access to data for machine characteristics follows the rules set in the consortium agreement. Consent to data access must first be provided by the owner, after verification of the identity of the recipient.
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
2.3. Making data interoperable	The selected formats of the research data, i.e., .mat and .csv allow to easily re-combine data coming from different data set and different origins. Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included. The development of new vocabulary specific to the project is not expected.
2.4. Increase data re-use	Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available. Some research data could be made available by the completion of the project. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published. In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

Title	Digital twin (control strategy)	Owner	POLITO
--------------	---------------------------------	--------------	--------

Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	Y	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The data regarding this section concerns the use of control strategies based off the permanent magnet virtual temperature sensing algorithm, aimed at improving vehicle performance. The virtual sensing method will be implemented using Simulink software or Python script and saved in the format of .slx or .py files. The developed algorithm will be used in vehicle simulation.</p> <p>Presentations and internal documents describing the virtual sensors and control strategies will be produced in .pptx and .docx formats. To compress a collection of files, .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>Given the model file format, the expected size is provisioned to fall into the tens of kB.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. The metadata will provide general information about the virtual sensors and an emphasis on their integration for adequate control of the electric machine. The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation, used for reference of development and implementation of the algorithm in the scope of control. Search keywords will be included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.						
	Data						
	The data for control strategies related to developed virtual sensing algorithms is not openly available until related scientific papers are published. The access to data for machine characteristics follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
	Metadata						
	The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
2.3. Making data interoperable	The selected formats of the research data, i.e., .mat allow to easily re-combine data coming from different data set and different origins. Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included. The development new vocabulary specific to the project is not expected.						
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data could be made available by the completion of the project. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>						

3. Data security
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.

Title	Simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the virtual sensing technologies					Owner	POLITO
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N

1. Data Summary
<p>The collection of data concerns the vehicle-level simulation to test new control strategies and new machine solutions for improved vehicle dynamics, safety and energy efficiency, in relation to the included virtual sensors. Production vehicle data will be collected from open resources to set up the vehicle model for target vehicle applications. Simulation results will be collected to analyse vehicle-level performances. The data are a useful resource for Horizon Europe projects such as HighScape and HiPE (with participation of POLITO, too, acting as a contact partner for this topic among these projects).</p> <p>The data are generated by simulation software at the vehicle level. Most of the data are numerical vectors in an output format such as .mat and .csv. Additional data types are performance indicators figures in .png format and tables in .csv or .xls format. Presentations and internal documents will be produced in .pptx and .docx formats. For collection of files in a compressed format, .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>To assess the success of the optimisation of EM-TECH components, data pre-collected from the baseline components and control strategies will be used for comparison. These can be either simulation or test bench data. Functional blocks are re-used for future similar projects.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of tens of MB per file generated from the temperature sensing algorithm integrated into the vehicle simulator.</p> <p>The data might be useful for the research community and engineers, to replicate specific experiments or benchmark their components or vehicles with the findings of EM-TECH, as well as for the EM-TECH participants that provide hardware and software components, for their future developments.</p>

2. FAIR data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation, used for reference of development and implementation of the algorithm, with an emphasis on its integration into the vehicle model. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.
	Data The data for vehicle-level simulations involving developed virtual sensing algorithms is not openly available until related scientific papers are published. The access to data for machine characteristics follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.

2.3. Making data interoperable	The selected formats of the research data, i.e., .mat allow to easily re-combine data coming from different data set and different origins. Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included. The development new vocabulary specific to the project is not expected.
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

5.5 Dataset related to PO5: Novel electric inverter/motor control functions based on virtual sensing technologies

Title	Design of the inverter for AFM				Owner	I&M	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>This collection of data refers to technical documentation about the AFM motor controller. Block diagrams for hardware will be provided in .pdf or .html formats. The dataset includes 3D CAD models for the mechanical design of the unit. SolidWorks and/or .step data formats will be used during development. Concerning the interfaces of the unit toward the system: connectors pinout documentation will be provided by mean of 2D drawings/tables in pdf format. The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-100 MB per file.</p> <p>Presentations and internal documents describing the inverter will be produced in .pptx and .docx formats. To compress a collection of files, .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>Existing data about current inverter family available at I&M will be used as baseline either for development and comparison purposes.</p>							
2. FAIR data							

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>To ensure effective data management, the identification of data will be based on naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. In the fields of EM-TECH, which primarily include automotive, electrical, and control engineering, there are limited availability of specific standards.</p> <p>Primarily intended for documentation purposes, metadata will serve as a reference during the algorithm's development and implementation.</p>
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with appropriate identification will be stored and exchanged within the coordinator's SharePoint, which serves as the central repository for the entire consortium.</p>
	<p>Data</p> <p>The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>
	<p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be restricted in situations where a specific participant utilizes parts of their core IP to generate the data, and as a result, these parts will be protected.</p> <p>In order to facilitate data retrieval and sharing, previously defined data dictionaries will be used to interpret dataset.</p>
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>The data generated in the project will not be publicly accessible and will not be usable by third parties.</p>
3. Data security	
<p>The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.</p>	

Title	Control strategy of the AFM inverter					Owner	I&M
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>This collection of data refers to technical documentation about the motor control strategies dedicated to AFM. Block diagrams for data driven software strategies and/or flow charts for control driven software strategies will be provided in .pdf or .html formats. Concerning the interfaces of the unit toward the system CAN line message matrix will be documented by standard .dbc format file. The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-10 MB per file.</p> <p>Presentations and internal documents describing the inverter will be produced in .pptx and .docx formats. To compress a collection of files, .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>Existing data about current inverter family available at I&M will be used as baseline either for development and comparison purposes.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>To ensure effective data management, the identification of data will be based on naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. In the fields of EM-TECH, which primarily include automotive, electrical, and control engineering, there are limited availability of specific standards.</p> <p>Primarily intended for documentation purposes, metadata will serve as a reference during the algorithm's development and implementation.</p>						

2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with appropriate identification will be stored and exchanged within the coordinator's SharePoint, which serves as the central repository for the entire consortium.
	Data The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be restricted in situations where a specific participant utilizes parts of their core IP to generate the data, and as a result, these parts will be protected. In order to facilitate data retrieval and sharing, previously defined data dictionaries will be used to interpret dataset.
2.4. Increase data re-use	The data generated in the project will not be publicly accessible and will not be usable by third parties.
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

Title	Simulation models for the AFM inverter					Owner	I&M
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>This collection of data refers to the digital twin model for simulation of motor controller dedicated to AFM. Simulink block diagrams (.slx) and/or matlab script (.m) will be provided. Surrogate models and functions to replace the original models will be used when considering the computation resources and/or IP protection. The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-20 MB per file.</p> <p>Presentations and internal documents describing the inverter will be produced in .pptx and .docx formats. To compress a collection of files, .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>Existing data about current inverter family available at I&M will be used as baseline either for development and comparison purposes.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>To ensure effective data management, the identification of data will be based on naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. In the fields of EM-TECH, which primarily include automotive, electrical, and control engineering, there are limited availability of specific standards.</p> <p>Primarily intended for documentation purposes, metadata will serve as a reference during the algorithm's development and implementation.</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with appropriate identification will be stored and exchanged within the coordinator's SharePoint, which serves as the central repository for the entire consortium.						
	Data						

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

	The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be restricted in situations where a specific participant utilizes parts of their core IP to generate the data, and as a result, these parts will be protected. In order to facilitate data retrieval and sharing, previously defined data dictionaries will be used to interpret dataset.
2.4. Increase data re-use	The data generated in the project will not be publicly accessible and will not be usable by third parties.
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

Title	Analysis, simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the AFM inverter					Owner	I&M
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>This collection of data refers to results coming from simulation and experimental activities. Data will be recorded as time series or numerical vectors in either .csv or Matlab (.mat) file formats. Supplementary data types include performance indicator images in .png format, as well as tables in .csv or .xls formats. CAN line data stream will be recorded in .tcr or .m4f format. The data size is expected to be in the order of 10-500 MB per file.</p> <p>Presentations and internal documents describing the inverter will be produced in .pptx and .docx formats. To compress a collection of files, .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>Existing data about current inverter family available at I&M will be used as baseline either for development and comparison purposes.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>To ensure effective data management, the identification of data will be based on naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. In the fields of EM-TECH, which primarily include automotive, electrical, and control engineering, there are limited availability of specific standards.</p> <p>Primarily intended for documentation purposes, metadata will serve as a reference during the algorithm's development and implementation.</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	Data with appropriate identification will be stored and exchanged within the coordinator's SharePoint, which serves as the central repository for the entire consortium.						
	Data						
	The access to data follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
	Metadata						
	The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						

2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be restricted in situations where a specific participant utilizes parts of their core IP to generate the data, and as a result, these parts will be protected. In order to facilitate data retrieval and sharing, previously defined data dictionaries will be used to interpret dataset.
2.4. Increase data re-use	The data generated in the project will not be publicly accessible and will not be usable by third parties.
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

5.6 Dataset related to PO6: Use of recycled permanent magnets in traction machines

Title	Recyclability / circularity designs				Owner	UG	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The collection of data serves the purpose of pursuing eco-design strategies to be implemented during the project. Data regarding current recycling praxis and state-of-the-art technologies will be collected from published scientific research and European statistics to define the baseline of the EoL-scenario. Data which serves the purpose of assessment of the EoL-stage within the LCA will be asked to the responsible partner in the form of a formular.</p> <p>Data will be presented in a .docx, .pptx or .xlsx with an expected maximal size per file of 20 MB.</p> <p>Data collected for the PO6 might be useful to scientific researchers and European institutions to adapt the legal framework of end-of-life vehicles to the particularities of the electric vehicle.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The metadata regarding the definition of the EoL-scenario will be referenced/tagged to allow the trackability of the data source for the project partners as well as the public.</p> <p>The metadata regarding the assessment of the LCA will be processed internally within the EM-Tech project and used to determine the environmental and monetary costs of the involved process. Therefore, metadata for the LCA will refer to the results of the LCA after processing the previously collected raw data.</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.						
	Data						
	The data regarding the LCA follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
	Metadata						
	The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
2.3. Making data interoperable	Technical data vocabularies will be previously defined, referenced or exemplified in order to avoid misinterpretations among the involved partners.						

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

	Qualified references will be pursued.
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Information about the procedure/experimental methodology followed to collect the necessary data for the LCA as well as data for the determination of the baseline/current praxis of the EoL-scenario will be facilitated.</p> <p>Data produced for the purpose of the PO6 is expected to be reused to develop new strategies regarding legal frameworks of waste management and for future projects which tackle exclusively recycling solutions for e-motors/permanent magnets.</p>
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

5.7 Dataset related to PO7: Novel electric drive control functions benefitting from the increased electric machine dynamics

Title	Control strategy of the IWM and AFM					Owner	USR/TUI	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	Y	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N	
1. Data Summary								
<p>The collection of data concerns the control strategies to improve vehicle dynamics, safety and energy efficiency, subject to new machine solutions developed in the project. Data regarding the target vehicles and the characterisation of the different prototypes or designs of new machines solutions will be collected for control design, in the form of vectors of numbers in the output format such as .csv or .mat (MATLAB data). The controller models will be coded using Simulink software and saved in the format of .slx files.</p> <p>Presentations and internal documents describing the control strategies will be mostly produced in .pptx and .docx formats. When containers were necessary .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-20 MB per file.</p>								
2. FAIR data								
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information about the control functions (e.g., ABS) and the control methods (e.g., nonlinear predictive control). The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords will be included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>							
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p>							
	<p>Data</p> <p>The data for new control strategies is not openly available until related scientific papers are published. The access to data for machine characteristics follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>							

	<p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>The selected formats of the research data, e.g., .mat and .csv allow to easily re-combine data coming from different data set and different origins. For the case of automotive and electric engineering, no specific, but only generic, standards are available. Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.</p>
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
<p>3. Data security</p>	
<p>The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.</p>	

Title	Simulation models of the IWM and AFM					Owner	USR/TUI
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
<p>1. Data Summary</p> <p>The collection of data concerns the build-up of the surrogate models of IWMs and AFMs to replace the original models when considering the computation resources, The surrogate models will be implemented as Simulink .slx format. The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-20 MB per file.</p>							
<p>2. FAIR data</p>							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information of IWMs and AFMs (e.g., category, rating, size). The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>						

2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.
	Data The access to data for machine characteristics follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

Title	Analysis, simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the IWM and AFM					Owner	USR/TUI
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The collection of data concerns the vehicle-level simulation to test new control strategies and new machine solutions for improved vehicle dynamics, safety and energy efficiency. Production vehicle data will be collected from open resources to set up the vehicle model for target vehicle applications. Simulation results will be collected to analyse vehicle-level performances. The data are a useful resource for the Horizon Europe projects HighScape (www.highscape.eu) and HiPE (www.hipeproject.eu).</p> <p>The data are generated by simulation software at the vehicle level. Most of the data have been and will be collected in the form of vectors of numbers in the output format .csv or of the software Matlab (.mat). Additional data types are performance indicators figures in .png format and tables in .csv or .xls format. Presentations and internal documents have been mostly produced in .pptx and .docx formats. When containers were necessary .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p>							

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

<p>To assess the success of the optimisation of EM-TECH components, data pre-collected from the baseline components and control strategies will be used for comparison. These can be either simulation or test bench data. Functional blocks are re-used for future similar projects.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-20 MB per file and up to 1-2 GB for files generated from CAD software. The total data size is expected to be in the order of tens of GB.</p> <p>The data might be useful for the research community and engineers, to replicate specific experiments or benchmark their components or vehicles with the findings of EM-TECH, as well as for the EM-TECH participants that provide hardware and software components, for their future developments.</p>	
<h3>2. FAIR data</h3>	
<p>2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>
<p>2.2. Making data accessible</p>	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p> <hr/> <p>Data</p> <p>The access to data of simulation and test results new control strategies follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p> <hr/> <p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>
<p>2.3. Making data interoperable</p>	<p>The selected formats of the research data, i.e., .mat, .csv etc. allow to easily re-combine data coming from different data set and different origins. For the case of automotive and electric engineering, no specific, but only generic, standards are available. Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such</p>

	as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

5.8 Dataset related to PO8: Digital twinning of electric drives

Title	Simulation models of the electric drive				Owner	AVL/TUI/USR	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
The collection of data concerns the detailed models of electric drives (IWMs, AFMs and mechanical transmissions) at the electrical, electronic, thermal and control levels. The component models in the format of dedicated software tools will be integrated using AVL toolchain. The data size is expected to be in the order of 10-100 MB per file.							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information of e-corner and e-axle drives (e.g., category, rating, size). The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.						
	Data The access to data for new electric drives follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.						
2.4. Increase data re-use	Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available. Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in						

	<p>relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
<p>The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.</p>	

Title	Digital twin of the electric drive (control strategy)				Owner	AVL/TUI/USR	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The collection of data concerns the development of the digital twins of electric drives. The digital twins include the XIL integration of components, the adaptive interfaces for coupling virtual and physical systems from different domains, and the extension of XIL concept by networking complex testing facilities. The data size is expected to be in the order of 10-100 MB per file.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata will provide general information of e-corner and e-axis drives. The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	<p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p>						
	Data						
	<p>The access to data for new electric drives follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						
	Metadata						
	<p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>						
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.</p>						
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p>						

	<p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

Title	Simulation and test results (component, system, vehicle level) for the Digital twinning of electric drives				Owner	AVL/TUI/USR	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>Production vehicle data will be collected from open resources to set up the vehicle model for target vehicle applications. Simulation and test results will be collected to analyse the performance of new electric drives. The data are a useful resource for Horizon Europe projects HighScope and HiPE.</p> <p>The data generated by simulation and tests will be collected in the form of vectors of numbers in the output format .csv or of the software Matlab (.mat). Additional data types are performance indicators figures, collected in tables in .csv and .xls format. Presentations and internal documents have been mostly produced in .pptx and .docx formats. When containers were necessary .zip is used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. These will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of 0.5-20 MB per file and up to 1-2 GB for files generated from CAD software. The total data size is expected to be in the order of tens of GB.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.						
	Data						
	The access to data of simulation and test results follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
	Metadata						

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

	The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
2.3. Making data interoperable	The selected formats of the research data, i.e., .mat, .csv etc. allow to easily re-combine data coming from different data set and different origins. For the case of automotive and electric engineering, no specific, but only generic, standards are available. Interoperability will be limited when a specific participant will use parts of its core IP to generate the data, and therefore these will be protected. Qualified references to data of new machine solutions of the project, to previous work and to public data will be included.
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

Title	Transmission virtual validation					Owner	AVL
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>For XIL integration, a black box torsional (= 1D) model will be provided based on the transmission concept which maximize the total efficiency. The black box model will use given speed and torque as an input and generate the dynamic response (dynamic rotational reactions) as output values.</p> <p>Documentation and presentations will be stored as both .pptx and .pdf.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of MBs.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. For the disciplines concerning EM-TECH (automotive, electrical, and control engineering mainly), only very generic standards are available. The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and will be optimised to be human readable, as opposed to machine readable. These would be of paramount importance to produce machine readable metadata to make the data discoverable by highly automatized database. Search keywords have been included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>						

2.2. Making data accessible	Repository Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.
	Data The access to data of simulation and test results follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
	Metadata The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.
2.3. Making data interoperable	Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software used to generate the models. The final design will include drawings.
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own polices.	

5.9 Dataset related to PO9: Engineering services for electric drive LCA and LCC

Title	LC(S)A reports for IWM and AFM					Owner	AVL/POLITO
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The input data regarding this section concerns the data to set up the LCA and LCC models comprising of life cycle material, energy and cost flows that will be collected, at first instance, from project partners and then from literature of previous LCA assessments with the aim of filling fill data gaps. The output data regarding this section concerns the LCA and LCC results of the target electric drive solutions (i.e., state-of-the-art IWMs and AFMs and EM-TECH IWM and AFM solutions) obtained through the development of the LCA and LCC models using SimaPro software. The LCA and LCC models are comprised of Life Cycle Inventories available in an output format such as .csv and .xlsx. The LCA and LCC results are environmental and cost impact figures that will be saved in the form of tables of numbers in the .xlsx format or .opju.</p>							

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

<p>Data collection forms have been produced and shared with project partners through .pptx and .xlsx formats. Presentations and internal documents describing the LCA and LCC models and results have been produced in .pptx and .docx formats. When containers were necessary, .zip will be used as the preferred extension. Other types of data are represented by the public deliverables produced in EM-TECH. Regarding the LCA assessments, the deliverables will be developed according to the standard ISO 14044 and 14044 and they will be made available in .pdf format.</p> <p>The data size is expected to be in the order of kB.</p>	
<h3>2. FAIR data</h3>	
<p>2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The data will be identified following naming conventions and keywords, in addition to relevant information (i.e., date, location, etc) in the file names and directory structures. The metadata will provide general information about the Life Cycle Inventory of the state-of-the-art and EM-TECH solutions and their environmental and cost impacts. The metadata produced are mainly for the scope of documentation and used for reference of development of the LCA and LCC models. Search keywords will be included in deliverable reports and relevant documents.</p>
<p>2.2. Making data accessible</p>	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator’s SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p> <p>Data</p> <p>The data for LCA and LCC results is not openly available until related scientific papers are published. Consent to data access must first be provided by the owner, after verification of the identity of the recipient.</p> <p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>
<p>2.3. Making data interoperable</p>	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software and parameters used to generate the specified data. The LCA models and deliverables developed for this project will be created using LCA standards such as ISO 14040 and 14044 and will therefore be interoperable by anyone with relevant LCA expertise. Results will be documented in form of graphs, figures and/or tables. Qualified references to previous work and to public data will be included. The development of a new vocabulary specific to the project is not expected.</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the LCA and LCC results will be re-usable by third parties. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p>
<h3>3. Data security</h3>	
<p>The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.</p>	

5.10 Dataset related to PO10: E Distributed XIL and innovative testing methodologies

Title	XIL mechanical design					Owner	TUI/USR/POLITO/UBATH/AVL	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data		N
1. Data Summary								
Documentation to the hardware-in-the-loop brake test rig, the powertrain test rig, the brake HIL and other								
2. FAIR data								
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be stored on the coordinator's SharePoint and will be available to each member of the consortium. Thus, access to the data is limited to the rights allocated by the coordinator and will only be granted to members of the consortium.</p> <p>No personal data and no ethical issues are identified.</p> <p>Data may be used in documentation, reports and publications.</p>							
2.2. Making data accessible	<p>Repository</p> <p>Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator's SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.</p>							
	<p>Data</p> <p>The access to data for new electric drives follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>							
	<p>Metadata</p> <p>The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.</p>							
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by the use of a detailed technical description of the test set-up and XIL test network, indicating the software by which the data will be generated. In this way it will be possible to reproduce the test conditions at a later date.</p> <p>The technical description will contain a description of the setup, the characteristics, the test and experiment conditions, the parameters of the test model and the controller.</p>							
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>							
3. Data security								

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.

Title	Real-time data during XIL distributed operation					Owner	TUI/USR/POLITO/UBATH/AVL	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N	
1. Data Summary								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation to testing environment, incl. specification of software, hardware and communication components; • Vehicle dynamics model incl. a full vehicle model and real-time versions of the models for the use in dSPACE environment; • Programme code of controllers 								
2. FAIR data								
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be stored on the coordinator's SharePoint and will be available to each member of the consortium. Thus, access to the data is limited to the rights allocated by the coordinator and will only be granted to members of the consortium. File version, as well as software version would be indicated in the name of the file.</p> <p>No personal data and no ethical issues are identified; Data may be used in documentation, reports and publications</p>							
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository							
	Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator's SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.							
	Data							
	The access to data for new electric drives follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.							
	Metadata							
	The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.							
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software used to generate the specified data. In this way, the possibility for further data processing will be preserved. The generated data will contain test and experiment conditions, test model and controller parameters. The processed data will be presented in the form of figures and graphs in reports suitable for the evaluation of the results obtained.</p>							
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible</p>							

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

	<p>only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
<p>The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.</p>	

Title	XIL test results for IWM					Owner	TUI/USR/POLITO/UBATH/AVL
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
Results of validation and testing of IWM in developed testing environment, incl. recorded signals of sensors and measurement techniques on test rigs							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be stored on the coordinator's SharePoint and will be available to each member of the consortium. Thus, access to the data is limited to the rights allocated by the coordinator and will only be granted to members of the consortium. Data collected by the operators of test rigs / setups would be collected and stored.</p> <p>No personal data and no ethical issues are identified; Data may be used in documentation, reports and publications</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator's SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.						
	Data						
	The access to data for new electric drives follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
	Metadata						
	The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software used to generate the specified data. In this way, the possibility for further data processing will be preserved.</p> <p>The generated data will contain test and experiment conditions, test model and controller parameters. The processed data will be presented in the form of figures and graphs in reports suitable for the evaluation of the results obtained.</p>						
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general,</p>						

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

	<p>after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

Title	XIL test results for AFM					Owner	TUI/USR/POLITO/UBATH/AVL
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
Results of validation and testing of AFM in developed testing environment, incl. recorded signals of sensors and measurement techniques on test rigs							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The data will be stored on the coordinator's SharePoint and will be available to each member of the consortium. Thus, access to the data is limited to the rights allocated by the coordinator and will only be granted to members of the consortium. Data collected by the operators of test rigs / setups would be collected and stored.</p> <p>No personal data and no ethical issues are identified; Data may be used in documentation, reports and publications</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	Data with a proper identifier will be stored and shared in the coordinator's SharePoint, the repository for the whole consortium. The coordinator manages the access and security of the data repository.						
	Data						
	The access to data for new electric drives follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
	Metadata						
	The access to metadata follows the rules set in the consortium agreement.						
2.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Interoperability will be ensured by using standard data formats, specifying the software used to generate the specified data. In this way, the possibility for further data processing will be preserved. The generated data will contain test and experiment conditions, test model and controller parameters. The processed data will be presented in the form of figures and graphs in reports suitable for the evaluation of the results obtained.</p>						
2.4. Increase data re-use	<p>Different license types are available for research data. In general, the data can be licensed to provide access for both research and commercial scope to the project participants, whereas licenses bounding the use to research scope will be enforced for the data that will be made publicly available. In general, any research data that will be produced, and shared at any level, will be associated with a license of relevant type (even if this means open access license), in case a participant is interested in making certain data available.</p> <p>Some research data, for example regarding the component and system testing, could be made available by the completion of the project, depending on the outcome of the testing sessions. An embargo of 3 years, depending on the publication/dissemination situation will be enforced. This is to allow the full</p>						

	<p>exploitation of the data by the project participants and the completion of the publication process in relevant scientific journals. This embargo period is reasonable given the type of information that will be produced in the project and the level of relevance that they retain throughout the years. In general, after the embargo period, the research data will be re-usable by third parties in a way that depends on their license type. The exceptions are represented by the research data that will be excluded from publication (representing the know-how of the specific participant) and the data that are accessible only after signing an NDA. The latter might be used but not re-published.</p> <p>In general, in the metadata for documentation, the processes to assure data quality are reported, such as specific testing arrangements and checks performed on the data.</p>
3. Data security	
The project coordinator will deal with the security of data stored on the EM-TECH SharePoint. Data belonging to individual participants will be secured following their own policies.	

5.11 Dataset related to project operation and CDE activities:

Title	Contact list with personal contact information				Owner	Coordinator / Meeting organizer	
Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	Y	Open Research Data	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>For efficient project operation the coordinator generated different contact lists that is used from the whole consortium to have easy access and overview of all contact information concerning the project operation (e.g., partners contact, advisory board contact) or specific activities (e.g., meeting with attendees list). The list typically consists of each consortium member’s company name, the acronym, the type of company and the country the firm is located at. On a more detailed level, it also collects sensitive data, such as personal data, from every person working for the project in terms of their name, e-mail address and possibly phone number. Further, such list can contain project specific or event specific information (e.g., role in the project such as work package lead, PSB board member and deputies, or participation (Y/N) to a specific event).</p> <p>This data will be exclusively useful for consortium members to look up contact persons and find e-mail addresses to copy and paste and will not be re-used for other projects. We expect the different lists to have up to 100 entries and the excel will have not more than 50KB. As mentioned, the list also contains sensitive data and will therefore be kept accessible for consortium members only and will not be public.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be stored on the coordinator’s SharePoint and will be accessible for each member of the consortium via a direct invitation from AVL. Therefore, the access to the data is limited to rights distributed by the coordinator and will only be granted to consortium members. There is no metadata created, no keywords will be provided, and the data will not be offered in a way that it can be harvested or indexed.						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository As mentioned, the data will be stored on AVL’s SharePoint, which acts as a trusted repository to which access is granted through direct invitation from the coordinator. Each member has to create an assigned identifier in order to login to the SharePoint and access the data.						
	Data The data will be available to all consortium members through the coordinator’s SharePoint to which each member has been granted access to via a direct invitation and will not be openly available. There are no restrictions on use during the project. The coordinator will maintain and update this list on their SharePoint until the administrative end of the project. The identity of the person accessing the SharePoint is validated through a two-step authentication according to AVL guidelines. There is no need for a data access committee.						
	Metadata As this dataset will contain very simple and clear data and will therefore have no need for metadata. It is purposed for internal communication only, there will be no data, nor metadata, be made public.						
2.3. Making data interoperable	The data is intended to be copied and pasted to simplify the process of accessing the right addressees. There will be no need for this data to interoperable and there are no qualified references to other data included.						
2.4. Increase data re-use	A re-use of the collected data is not planned. The data collected is only suitable for this particular project and cannot be used for any other, as there will be other consortium members and individuals working for it. The data will not be used by third parties at any time. The list will be kept up to date at any time, as there can always fluctuation of staff.						

3. Data security
Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data is available during project operation, and a back-up is created at the end of the project (available only through dedicated request to IT).

Title	Project management related datasets				Owner	Project management team	
Confidentiality	N	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N	Open Research Data	N

1. Data Summary

In order to grant an effective project process flow, several lists have been created on the coordinators SharePoint to offer an easy overview for the project partner and keep due dates and main activities in sight. These lists are and contain:

- Deliverable list: deliverable number, title, information about the lead, nature of the deliverable (R, DMP or DEM), dissemination level (public or sensitive), date of delivery in months and current status,
- Milestone list: milestone number, milestone name, work package, date, date in months, means of verification, status,
- Risk list: number and title, likelihood, work packages involved, mitigation measure and status,
- List of dissemination activities: title, date, type of activity, description of dissemination activity,
- List of publications: title, authors, type of publication, title of journal/proceedings/book, number, date or frequency of the journal/proceedings/book, place of publication, publisher, year, ISBN, DOI, kind of publication, link.

The purpose of these datasets is to offer a quick overview on certain project related topics. The data that is in this list has been created for this project and is in the format of a list on SharePoint. The data will only be useful for project partners and will be of none-use when the project is completed.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data will be stored on the coordinator’s SharePoint and will be accessible for each member of the consortium via a direct invitation from AVL. Therefore, the access to the data is limited to rights distributed by the coordinator and will only be granted to consortium members. There is no metadata created, no keywords will be provided and the data will not be offered in a way that it can be harvested or indexed.
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository As mentioned, the data will be stored on AVL’s SharePoint, which acts as a trusted repository to which access is granted through direct invitation from the coordinator. Each member has to create an assigned identifier in order to login to the SharePoint and access the data.
	Data The data will be available to all consortium members through the coordinator’s SharePoint to which each member has been granted access to via a direct invitation and will not be openly available. There are no restrictions on use during the project. The coordinator will keep this list on their SharePoint until the administrative end of the project. The identity of the person accessing the SharePoint is validated through a two-step authentication according to AVL guidelines. There is no need for a data access committee.
	Metadata As this dataset contains very simple and clear data and will therefore have no need for metadata. It is purposed for internal purposes only, there will be no data, nor metadata, be made public.
2.3. Making data interoperable	The data is intended to grant an overview of all deliverables, milestones, risks, dissemination activities and publications and offers all project partners a place where they can easily access and find information. There will be no need for this data to interoperable and there are no qualified references

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

	to other data included.
2.4. Increase data re-use	A re-use of the collected data is not planned. The data collected is only suitable for this particular project and cannot be used for any other. The data will not be used by third parties at any time. The lists will be kept up to date at any time, as the project progresses.
3. Data security	
Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data is available during project operation, and a back-up is created at the end of the project (available only through dedicated request to IT).	

Title	Materials for Communication / Dissemination / Exploitation activities and reporting (e.g., deliverables, scientific papers, public presentations, marketing material, website content)						
Owner	Partner having created the material	Confidentiality	Y	Cyber-security	N	Privacy	N
1. Data Summary							
<p>The project will have several results and information that will be publicly available such as certain deliverables, scientific papers, public presentations, marketing materials and content on the project’s website. These communication and dissemination materials can contain information from the project in various forms such as papers, flyers, roll-ups, presentations or as description on the project website. A dedicated release process for reporting / for dissemination activities has been defined in the consortium agreement, and the project partners must be notified before the publication and can object within a given period. If no objection is made, the publication is permitted.</p> <p>A dedicated community for the EM-TECH project has been created on the Zenodo platform where the Deliverables and scientific papers will be published. Links to these entries on Zenodo will also be available on the project website as well as shared on LinkedIn.</p>							
2. FAIR data							
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Each material published on Zenodo will receive a dedicated DOI.</p> <p>It is very likely, that metadata will be created out of the results of the project. However, no such data exists at the moment.</p> <p>Keywords will be used on the project website and for published results in order to make results more findable. It is not planned to offer metadata in a way that it can be harvested or indexed.</p>						
2.2. Making data accessible	Repository						
	The data will be stored on the project SharePoint for efficient access through the consortium, and further the released public material will be stored on Zenodo. Scientific papers might be available through dedicated repositories such as IEEE Explore , ACM Digital Library or SAE International .						
	Data						
	Data will be openly available, especially deliverables and scientific papers that are planned to be public as well as marketing materials to reach a broader audience and make the project’s results more visible. The data regarding dissemination is produced to speak for the project even long after the end of the project.						
	Metadata						
	The results that arises from the project are meant to create an impact in research that might follow. Therefore, the data will stay on the project’s website as well as on Zenodo even after the project ends. There is no particular software needed to access or read the data.						

D 1.2 – Data Management Plan

2.3. Making data interoperable	Not relevant for this dataset.
2.4. Increase data re-use	Knowledge reuse will be the focus. This will be achieved by increasing the exposure (number of view) and reference (number of citations) of the generated material.
3. Data security	
Security rules for the dedicated repositories are out of our domain of influence. Regarding project SharePoint, Data security policies follows the IT policies of the coordinator (AVL). Data is available during project operation, and a back-up is created at the end of the project (available only through dedicated request to IT).	

6 Data flow charts

In the course of the project, three groups of data flows have been identified:

1. Data flows for the management of contact lists, including the interaction with the user to add / remove / correct new contact points, see Figure 4;
2. Data flows for the release of project related documentation and CDE material, see Figure 5
3. Data flows for the management of technical project outcomes (PO1 – PO10 from Section 5), see Figure 6

Figure 4: Data flow chart for contact list management

Dataset for project documentation and CDE material
(e.g., deliverables, scientific publication, marketing material, website content)

Figure 5: Data flow chart for release of project documentation and CDE materials

Dataset related to creation and validation of project outcomes
(e.g., design file, simulation models, control strategy, V&V related data)

Figure 6: Data flow chart for creation and validation of technical project outcomes

7 Conclusion

The first version of the DMP targets (a) the identification of relevant datasets to be managed in EM-TECH, (b) the presentation of the overall methodology introduced by the European Commission, and (c) the dataset analysis at project's start (Month M06).

Targeted audiences and respective targets are:

- At **project management level**, to ensure that all the project activities (and the respective datasets created in this context) have been carefully planned at operational level. Especially, to ensure that no major activities are missing, that each activity and dataset has an owner and defined processing rules.
- At **partner level**, to raise awareness on data management and provide guidance on relevant dataset categories in the project and how to manage the datasets accordingly.
- At **stakeholder level**, to provide information about the datasets managed in the project, and especially the datasets planned to be shared in the context of the open research strategy. The sharing of project documentation (e.g., deliverables, scientific publications) and sharing of datasets is an explicit strategy to strengthen the innovation ecosystem around the EM-TECH project.

During the creation of the deliverable, a list of >30 datasets has been identified and linked to expected project outcomes or to the project operation (management, CDE activities). As suggested in the Horizon Europe Template's general comments on "other research outputs", the scope of this document has been extended to address these, as well.

During the analysis of the datasets, three main categories of criticality have been identified:

- (a) Datasets with **confidentiality issues**; Unintended disclosure of the dataset might lead to a loss of competitiveness for one or more partner(s).
- (b) Datasets with **cyber-security issues**; Modification of the dataset (unintended or malicious) might lead to issues related to loss of vehicle integrity or emergence of safety risk during operation.
- (c) Datasets with **personal data**; Unintended access might lead to privacy issues, lack of management might lead to non-compliance regarding relevant national and European regulations (e.g., GDPR).

A general approach has been designed for the management of each of these three criticalities and has been refined at dataset level if required. Parallel to this, datasets planned to be published for open research data (and that could be impacted by access rights exercised by third parties) have been identified. Open research data will support ecosystem engagement, and therefore strengthen impact generation.

This document will be revised at M18 (project mid-term) and at M30 (shortly before end of the project) to reflect the advance in the project and consolidate dataset management accordingly. Another aspect will be the decision to open specific datasets to support the Communication and Dissemination strategy, especially focusing on stakeholder engagement.

7.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

There are no deviations regarding the content of this deliverable.

Bibliography

- [1] Official Journal of the European Union, Directive (EU) 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure, [Link](#)
- [2] Official Journal of the European Union, NIS Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, [Link](#)
- [3] European Commission, COM(2022) 454, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020), Sept. 2022, [Link](#)
- [4] Official Journal of the European Union, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), [Link](#)
- [5] Official Journal of the European Union, PSI Directive n° 2 (Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information, [Link](#)
- [6] Official Journal of the European Union, Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act), [Link](#)
- [7] European Commission, COM(2022) 68, Data Act Proposal (Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonized rules on fair access to and use of data, February 2022, [Link](#)
- [8] Horizon Europe, Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0, May 5th, 2021, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON>